

Use of MODIS imagery to investigate fire regime. Case study Eastern part of South Kordofan State-Sudan

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Date Received, December 12, 2015 Date Accepted, February 3, 2016

I. INTRODUCTION

Abstract- South Kordofan state in Sudan includes different land cover and land use types, There was no information available on when, where, how often and how much wildfires burn and the relationship between fire incidence and plant growth. The objective of this study is to investigate the fire regime (extent, seasonality and frequency of wildfires) using remote sensing and GIS techniques through MODIS data. The study was conducted in Eastern part of South Kordofan State for season (2000-2001) to (2013-2014), in order to generate fire history and burned area maps, a collection of 45 images per each season was processed (630 images for fourteen seasons) were analyzed to extract the burned area. ENVI 4.7 and ARCMAP10.0 software were used for image processing, analyzing and maps production. The study showed that the largest burned area was in season (2012-2013) and the then season (2003-2004) and the lowest burned area was in season (2013 - 2014) and then season (2000-2001). In order to generate a fire frequency map each three successive number of burn times have been classified into a Categories. The study revealed various important results about fire regime such as the fire season which is generally starts in mid-September and continues up to the beginning of May with peak in November. The frequency map revealed that the higher fire frequency is located in Eastern, western and Southern parts of study area, look like a crescent and the least frequency burned area is located in the northern parts.

Index Terms: Fire regime, remote sensing, GIS techniques and Land/use/ cover change

Fire has an important role to play in nature, land management to maintain the functioning of ecological processes (1). However fire is responsible for the destruction of 250,000 tons of plant material annually. In addition to the negative environmental impacts and socioeconomic effects as damage or destruction of villages, which are built from grass and wooden materials. Fire also can cause soil erosion, loss of biological diversity, release of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases, damage of recreational and amenity values (2).

The fire regime includes the extent, seasonality, frequency, intensity, and spatial distribution of fires. The integrated fire management plan cannot be prepared and the ecological effects of the fire could not identified without good knowledge of fire regime. Satellite images could detect changes in land surface due to the fire occurrence. Such changes include removal of vegetation cover and burned material deposit. The detectable changes are then used for mapping burned areas. (3)

Although the Eastern part of Southern Kordofan State is suffering from wildland fire, but there is lack of information and the fire regime is not investigated yet. Fire season starts immediately after the end of the rainy season when the grasses become drier and that is usually occurs at the end of September or the beginning of October. Increased grass biomass in the prevalence of dry Northeastern wind and high temperature will reduce humidity and hence increase the fire risk (4). The pastoralist Ignite fire during their movement in the area for cooking, repel insects, fighting ticks and also by burning dry grass to get fresh sprout (5).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

South kordofan state is Located between the latitudes 9^o to 13^o N and longitudes 27^o to 33^o E with an area of 141, 096 km² (6).The population according to the census in 1993 was about 1,003,560 rose to 1,151,330 in the census of 2002 rose to 2.500,000 in census of 2008, about 17.4% of them live in urban areas, 79.3% in rural and 3.3% are nomads (7). This study is directed towards the use of remote sensing and geographic information systems (GIS) through MODIS data to document the history of fire and produce maps of burned areas in Eastern part of South Kordofan State for season (2000-2001) to (2013-2014). ENVI 4.7 and Arc map 10.0(Arc map) were used for processing and analyzing the images to produce the final maps. Images acquired by MODIS sensor were used to map the burned areas. Collection of 45 images per each season is processed (585 images for thirteen seasons) and analyzed to extract the burned area. MODIS 8 days surface reflectance product 250 m spatial resolution images were ordered and freely downloaded from the Web site (<https://reverb.echo.nasa.gov/api/>) for each season (from August 28 to April first next year) (8)The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) formula was used via ENVI 4.7 band math to produce the required images. The following mathematical expression was used:

$$\text{(Float (b2)-float (b1)) / (float (b2) +float (b1))}$$

Where

B1=Band1 (Red)

B2=Band2 (Near infrared)

In order to detect the burned areas within 8 days each earlier NDVI image was subtracted from previous

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Burned area mapping was a combination of visual and digital interpretations to identify the burned areas from MODIS image. The burned areas in the original images appear with black tones. The result described in the study enable precise identification of the exact

one and the results were saved in change detection images for further processing. A color density slice was created by identifying the pixel of the lowest value and the one with the highest value of change detection with in the burned area inside the image which was later saved as a class image.

The regions of interests were drawn around the real burned areas in order to mask out the noise which look similar to burned area. Unburned areas which have values similar to that of the burned areas were removed (masked out) and new images free of noise were created.

To the multiple burned area mapping that usually occurred at the margin were removed using the ENVI4.7 function (b1 gt 0), which assign Digital Number(DN) equal to one for all pixels having DN greater than zero.

The monthly burned area image for each season was generated by summing up all burned areas detected between all successive images within the same month.

The total burned area image was generated by summing up all burned areas detected between all successive images within the same season. This procedure was repeated for each fire season.

The resulting monthly and total burned area images were converted from raster to vector (shape-files) to be used in ArcGIS software 10.0 to calculate burned area and also to generate the final burned area maps.

In order to create a fire frequency map the Burned area of each season is summed in one image. The DN of this image represents the number of times burned.

burned areas in each image from which the total burned areas maps produced and identified by the starting and ends date within the total burned.

The fire season this generally starts in mid-September and continues up to beginning of May with a peak of burned areas in November. This is attributed to the fact that most of the grass in the area becomes drier at this time of the year (table 1).

Table (1) the starting and ends date with the total burnt area for each season

Season	Start Date	End Date	Burned Area km2
2000-2001	13.Sep.2000	8. May.2001	5,018,076
2001-2002	5.Sep.2000	30.Apr.2001	5,610,426
2002-2003	7.Sep.2000	5.May.2001	5,953,451
2003-2004	13.Sep.2000	8.May.2001	8,412,420
2004-2005	8.Sep.2000	6.May.2001	8,087,373
2005-2006	12.Sep.2000	1.May.2001	7,810,785
2006-2007	5.Sep.2000	8.May.2001	6,750,103
2007-2008	12.Sep.2000	7.May.2001	6,576,176
2008-2009	9.Sep.2000	30.Apr.2001	5,523,597
2009-2010	10.Sep.2000	2.May.2001	6,421,514
2010-2011	13.Sep.2000	3.May.2001	5,823,368
2011-2012	5.Sep.2000	8.May.2001	6,379,817
2012-2013	6.Sep.2000	6.May.2001	10,197,951
2013-2014	8 .sep.2000	1.May.2001	4,991,671

Fig (1)The seasonally burned area in 2000_2001 to 2013_2014

The study shows that the increase burned area was in season (2012-2013) and the decrease burned area was in season (2013 - 2014) (Fig 1) this may be attributed to the rain fluctuation which influences the vegetation cover density .The main activities in the area are

charcoal production and clearing the lands for agriculture and which are the main causes behind outbreak of fires. (9)

Fig (2) the burned area during the months overall the seasons

It is well clear from months Maps that the hilly burned area is in November (fig 2, 3) due to existence high biomass of vegetation is senescent and weather very dry. Also clear that fires in the form of patches always happens at the beginning of the dry season as a result of the presence of some low-lying areas that retain moisture and water. The Slash and burn for

agriculture that is practiced in the South-East of the study area, causes an increase in fire activity at the end of the dry season in February, which concurs with the preparation of the fields for the next crop season (10)

Fig (3) Total burned area map from (2000-2014)

Fig (4) Map of fire frequency

It is clear from the frequency map that the higher frequency burned area was located in Eastern, Western and Southern parts of study area in the shape of a crescent due to dense of forests and grasslands and pastoralists movements, who might cause fire due to cooking, repelling insect and burning dry grasses to get fresh one. Least frequent burned area was located in the northern parts of the study area

associated with the cultivation area while the medium frequent burned area is in the middle part of the study area and is associated with small holdings and population. (Fig 4) and (Fig 5)

Fig (5) the percentage of frequency burned area in the study area

VI. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, wild fires are largely extensive in most parts of the study area. The fire season starts normally in mid of September and lasts towards the end of May the most severely burned area is spread outside the cultivated area because the farmer usually protect their farms from being burned and MODIS 8day surface reflectance 250 m spatial resolution images are show high efficiency in burned area mapping. Study describing the plant structure which is affected by fire needs to be carried out.

Recommendations

More investigation is needed to determine the various causes of wild fire as well as the social impacts of wild fire needs to be investigated, in additional that the positive and negative impacts of wild fire on flora and fauna needs more detailed studies and More investigations is needed for non-burned areas having the same change detection value as the burned areas, so more investigation is needed to check the possibility of using landsat8 images in burned area mapping.

V. REFERENCES

- (1) Pausas Juli. G and Keeley Jon E.(2009). A Burning Story ,History of Life. Bioscience. Volume 59, Issue 7 Pp. 593-601.
- (2) Fire management global assessment 2006, (FAO 2006)
- (3) Evan J. Frost and Rob Sweeney (2000)(Wildwood Environmental Consulting84 4th Street Ashland, OR 97520
- (4) Worldwide science.org sample records for semi-arid Sudan .Wikipedia (December 2010) (Wildfire)
- (5) International Institute of Rural Reconstruction (2002) Managing dry land resources, an extension manual for eastern and southern Africa, ISBN 9966-9705-2-5
- (6) (International Journal of Agriculture Innovations and Research Volume 2, Issue 5, ISSN (Online) 2319-1473. Geohive Decennial Population Sudan
- (7) Abdel Raouf Bello, Development as historical process in the Nuba mountains region in Sudan
- (8) (<https://reverb.echo.nasa.gov/api/>)
- (9) A. Thulstrup and W.J. Henry, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (Apr 06, 2015) Women’s Access to Wood Energy during Conflict and Displacement: Lessons from Yei County, South Sudan Unasylva 243/244, Vol. 66, 2015/1–2
- (10) Daldoum Mohamed Ahamed (23-Apr-2015) Effects of fires on the Soil Physical and Chemical Properties and the Soil Seed Bank in Albaja Area at White Nile State, Sudan UOFK